

Percentage of nymphs becoming adults and the developmental period were recorded.

Neem treatment significantly reduced GLH and BPH egg laying, and nymph emergence and development (see figure). Fewer eggs were laid on plants sprayed with NSB at 5,000 ppm. No GLH nymphs became adults on

seedlings treated with either NSB or NLB extracted from dried leaves at 500 ppm; 16% of the nymphs developed on seedlings treated with NLB extracted from fresh leaves at 500 ppm. Development on seedlings treated with NLB from dried and from fresh leaves at 2,500 ppm was completely suppressed.

BPH development was reduced to 20% with 2,500 ppm NLB from dried leaves and to 39% with NLB from fresh leaves. No BPH nymphs developed on seedlings treated with 2,500 ppm NSB. □

Color morphism of rice swarming armyworm larvae

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Identification of *Spodoptera mauritia acronyctoides* (Gueneé) larvae collected in the field is often difficult, because of color variations. We reared newly hatched larvae individually to the last instar on 35-d-old TN1 rice. The insects were kept at an average 28 °C temperature and 80% relative humidity.

Color patterns on seven abdominal areas—three dorsal (median, subdorsal, dorsolateral) and four lateral (laterodorsal, midlateral, laterobasal, basal) M were recorded daily (see figure).

Lateral view of *S. m. acronyctoides* larva: dorsum (1) median, (2) subdorsal, (3) dorsolateral; lateral (4) midlateral, (5) laterodorsal. (6) laterobasal, and (7) basal. IIRRI, 1989.

Bodies of 1st- and 2d-instar larvae were green. However, the 2d-instar larvae had a reddish violet posterior half laterodorsal and whitish laterobasal.

Third-instar larvae exhibited four color morphs. The first was yellow-green with brownish violet laterodorsal and pinkish laterobasal. The other

color morphs were a combination of green, dull brown, brownish violet, and brownish green. Laterodorsal and laterobasal color bands were the most stable in the four color morphs observed. Traces of subdorsal black semilunar spots were already discernible on color morphs II and III.

Five color morphs were exhibited by 4th- and 5th-instar larvae (see table). Black semilunar spots were, prominent subdorsally on the first three color morphs but were replaced by a thin black line on the fourth color morph. The prominent broad, semilunar spots with black laterodorsal band in mature 5th-instar larvae were the most important distinguishing character of *S. m. acronyctoides* larvae. Color morph III was the most dominant. □

Color polymorphism in the 4th and 5th larval instars of *Spodoptera mauritia acronyctoides*. IIRRI greenhouse, Jun-Jul 1988.

Abdominal region	Color morph				
	I	II	III	IV	V
Dorsum					
Median	Grayish brown	Dull brown	Dull brown	Tinged pink and violet	Tinged pink and violet
Subdorsal	Very black sublunar spots	Dirty brown with black lunar spots	Dirty brown with black lunar spots	Greenish with thin black line beneath	Dark green with 4 black lunar spots on 1/3 of body anteriorly
Dorsolateral	Light grayish brown	Dull green	Dull brown	Dull green	Dull green
Lateral					
Midlateral	Dark grayish brown, light beneath grayish brown	Dark green and beneath is dull green line	Tinged green and brown	Greenish	Dark green and dull green beneath
Laterodorsal	Black	Black	Black	Black	Black
Laterobasal	Grayish brown	Dull brown	Dull brown	Dark pinkish violet	Dark pinkish violet
Basal	Dark greenish	Dull greenish	Brownish green	Greenish	Dark green
n	36	71	175	35	23